

Date of publication xxxx 00, 0000, date of current version xxxx 00, 0000.

Digital Object Identifier 10.1109/ACCESS.2017.Doi Number

State of Health Estimation for Lithium-ion Batteries Based on Healthy Features and Long Short-Term Memory

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This work was supported in part by the National Natural Science Foundation of China (No. 61763021 and No. 51775063), in part by the National Key R&D Program of China (No. 2018YFB0104000), in part by the Science and Technology Research Program of Chongqing Education Commission (No. KJQN201901539) and in part by the EU-funded Marie Skłodowska-Curie Individual Fellowships Project under Grant 845102-HOEMEV-H2020-MSCA-IF-2018.

ABSTRACT Precise estimation of state of health (SOH) are of great importance for proper operation of lithium-ion batteries equipped in electric vehicles. For real applications, it is however difficult to estimate battery SOH due to stochastic operation, which in turn speeds up aging process of the battery. To attain the precise SOH estimation, an efficient estimation manner based on machine learning is proposed in this study. Firstly, the voltage profile during charging and discharging process and incremental capacity variation are acquired through the cycle life test, and the healthy features correlating to battery degradation are extracted. Secondly, the grey relation analysis and entropy weight method are employed to analyze the healthy features. Finally, the long short-term memory is established to achieve the SOH estimation of battery. The experimental results highlight that the proposed method can effectively predict the battery SOH with preferable accuracy, stability and robustness.

INDEX TERMS Healthy features (HFs), grey relational analysis (GRA), entropy weight method (EWM), long short-term memory (LSTM), state of health (SOH).

NOMENCLATURE

A. ABBREVIATIONS

SOH	state of health	RUL	remaining useful life
HFs	healthy features	SP	single particle
GRA	grey relational analysis	GPR	Gaussian process regression
EWM	entropy weight method	SVM	support vector machine
LSTM	long short-term memory	IC	incremental capacity
EVs	electric vehicles	HFs	healthy features
BMS	battery management system	NN	neural networks
SEI	solid electrolyte interphase	ARMA	autoregressive moving average model
SOC	state of charge	RNNs	recurrent NNs
SOP	state of power	GRA	grey relational analysis
PF	particle filter	EWM	entropy weight method
		CC	constant current
		CV	constant voltage
		HPPC	hybrid power pulse characterization

UDDS	urban dynamometer driving schedule
MAE	maximum absolute error
MSE	mean square error
RMSE	root mean square error

B. SYMBOLS

Q_{cur}	the current maximum available capacity
Q_{nom}	the nominal capacity of the battery
F_1	the duration of CC charging process
F_2	the ratio of the CC charging time to the total charge time
F_3	the discharge duration of voltage drop
f	a mapping function from capacity to voltage
f^{-1}	the reverse function of f
V_l	the lower voltage boundary of voltage interval
V_h	the higher voltage boundary of voltage interval
$Q_{V_l \rightarrow V_h}$	the charge capacity in the voltage interval
Δt	the time duration when the voltage raises from V_l to V_h
F_4	IC peak value
F_5	the corresponding voltage of IC peak value
i	the cycle times
j	the j th HF
w_j	the entropy weight value for j th HF
h_{t-1}	the last output of cell state
x_t	the current cell input
f_t	the outputs of forget gate
σ	the sigmoid function
W_f	the weight matrix of forget gate
b_f	the bias of forget gate
i_t	the sigmoid layer of input gate

a_t	the output of tanh layer for the input gate
W_i	the weight matrix of sigmoid layer of input gate
W_C	the weight matrix of tanh layer of input gate
b_i	the bias of sigmoid layer of input gate
b_C	the bias of tanh layer of input gate
C_t	the current cell state
h_t	the output of LSTM at time t
W_o	the weight matrix of the output layer
b_o	the bias of output layer
o_t	the sigmoid layer of output gate
h_{t-1}	the learning rates of ω^2
$J(\theta)$	the objective function with θ
g_t	the gradient with parameter θ_{t-1}
m_t	the exponential moving average of gradient
v_t	the exponential moving average of squared gradient
β_1	the exponential decay factors accounting for weight distribution
β_2	the exponential decay factors that controls the influence incurred by squared gradient
\hat{m}_t	the modified values of m_t
\hat{v}_t	the modified values of v_t
α	the learning rate of Adam algorithm
ε	a smooth coefficient
R^2	goodness-of-fit
n	the total sample number
y_i	the real SOH value
\hat{y}_i	the predicted SOH value of LSTM
\bar{y}_i	the sampling average value

I. INTRODUCTION

Lithium-ion batteries have been widely equipped in electric vehicles (EVs) due to their advantages of high energy, power density and long lifespan [1-3]. An effective battery management system (BMS) is critical to ensure safe efficient operation of lithium-ion batteries. The battery state estimation, as one of the most important tasks of BMS, contributes greatly to safe operation and charge/discharge optimization. Among all the status indexes, state of health (SOH), indicating the current battery healthy status by means of the ratio of current full capacity over nominal value [4], acts as an important criterion on quantifying the battery lifespan and predicting remaining driving ranges of EVs [5, 6].

As is the case with most mechanical and electrical facilities, degradation of lithium-ion batteries is an irreversible process closely correlating to their internal electro-chemical reactions and daily operations [7]. During repetitive charging and discharging operations, side reaction continually happens between electrodes and electrolyte, leading to thickness increase of the solid electrolyte interphase (SEI) layer and loss of recyclable lithium-ions. On the other hand, repetitive cycling operation gives rise to morphology change of electrodes, such as porosity decrease, crack propagation and waste of active electrode materials [8, 9]. Meanwhile, extreme operating conditions like over charge/discharge, high/low temperature operation and high mechanical pressure can accelerate battery degradation as well [10]. Furthermore, due to complex operation conditions and degradation mechanism such as time-varying current, the stochastic discharge depth

and relaxation effect [11], it is difficult to establish accurate models to describe degradation process of lithium batteries. However, capacity degradation modeling based on the Wiener process can well describe the lithium-ion battery capacity degradation process [12, 13]. Refs. [14, 15] design the prediction method based on the Wiener process, and achieve the accurate prediction of battery SOH and remaining useful life (RUL). Accurate prediction of battery SOH is beneficial for health management, avoidance from catastrophic dangerous hazards and extension of lifespan. Furthermore, accurate SOH also facilitates estimation of other states, including state of charge (SOC) and state of power (SOP) [16]. However, given complexity and coupling features existing in inner electrochemical reactions of batteries, comprehensive investigation and clear expression of battery degeneration mechanism have not been systematically revealed yet. Besides, different types of lithium-ion batteries imply complex degeneration mechanisms due to their different inner structures and materials, making it intractable to precisely estimate SOH. Currently, popular SOH prediction methods can be classified into two categories, i.e., experimental methods and model-based estimation methods [17]. Experimental methods require a large number of tests to analyze the aging behavior of battery. Due to the need of experimental equipment and great difference between actual driving conditions and laboratory environments, the experimental methods are difficult to implement onboard. However, they can be used to investigate aging mechanisms and provide theoretical basis for model-based methods.

The model-based methods can be divided into adaptive algorithms and data driven methods. In general, adaptive algorithms combine mathematic models and numerical filters, such as Kalman filter, particle filter (PF) and Gaussian filter, to track the degradation tendency of battery. These filters can adaptively evaluate the confidence interval of sectional data according to the measured data and model credibility. In essence, adaptive algorithms rely largely on electrochemical models and equivalent circuit models, and require additional closed-loop control and feedback to achieve reliable prediction. Ref. [18] introduces an electrochemical model to simulate the battery charge and discharge process, and then a novel PF based framework is proposed to predict the RUL. Experimental results highlight that the proposed algorithm performs higher prediction precision, compared with conventional PFs. Ref. [19] introduces an adaptive particle learning algorithm by adjusting the particle number in each iteration to lessen computational intensity. Likewise, to further improve the prediction precision, the unscented PF is introduced to predict the battery RUL within 5% error [20]. Ref. [21] proposes the naive Bayes model to predict battery SOH and RUL under different environment temperatures and different discharge current rates. Ref. [8] combines the lithium-ion loss model derived from the SEI layer and the single particle (SP) model considering electrolytic physics to quickly predict the capacity fade and voltage profile variation

with high accuracy. Although these adaptive algorithms show favorable capability of characterizing the physical and chemical variation of battery, an accurate degeneration method is difficult to build for reliable SOH prediction all the time [22, 23].

Instead, data driven methods usually build black box models between input variables and objectives. Then, the advanced classification, machine learning and intelligent optimization algorithms will be applied to find the mapping relationship between inputs and targets, thereby realizing accurate prediction with the premise of enough training data. For SOH estimation, data driven methods do not require knowledge with respect to detailed battery degeneration mechanism and depend only on enough operational degradation data [24]. Usually, these methods extract key characteristic information of battery degradation from huge data sets by means of machine learning algorithms. Gaussian process regression (GPR) and support vector machine (SVM) are two commonly employed methods to establish the battery degradation model. In [25], partial incremental capacity (IC) of batteries is employed to analyze the degradation trend, and a dual GPR algorithm is implemented to predict the SOH and RUL simultaneously. To guarantee the accuracy and effectiveness, Ref. [26] analyzes the characteristic variation during charge and extracts feature variables based on the charging curve, then the GPR is employed to attain the SOH prediction. Ref. [27] selects the peak value and corresponding locations in the IC curve as the healthy features (HFs), optimizes the hyper parameters in the GPR algorithm by means of the conjugate gradient method and multi-island genetic algorithm, and finally attains the SOH estimation. Ref. [28] constructs the data set of battery operation under different conditions and extracts the key characteristics from voltage and temperature data. Then, the battery RUL and SOH is predicted based on the classification and regression of SVM. According to the voltage variation in the charging process, Ref. [10] establishes the SVM model considering different voltage intervals. With the help of grid search algorithm, the model parameters are derived to find the optimal voltage confidence interval for SOH prediction. In addition to GPR and SVM, other data driven algorithms, such as neural networks (NN) [29], autoregressive moving average model (ARMA) [4], ensemble learning [3] and random forest [30], are also extensively investigated for SOH application. All of these data driven methods need to extract specific features to train the model and build up the mapping function between SOH and feature variables. Only if the characteristic parameters are extracted reliably, the SOH can be possibly predicted then. For these data driven methods, although accurate understanding of battery degradation mechanism is not needed, large amounts of valid data are still indispensable to train the model and it becomes the main bottleneck of applying data driven methods that needs to be tackled [17]. In addition, how to effectively extract HFs from historical testing data still remains a challenging task.

To now, battery capacity and internal resistance are usually chosen as HFs owing to their strong correlation with SOH [31]. However, it should be noted that in real applications, battery capacity and internal resistance are difficult to acquire. The capacity is usually calculated by means of full charge and discharge cycle experiments, which seldom happen in actual operation. As for internal resistance, it is also almost impossible to be directly measured when the battery is grouped in modules or packs [32]. Considering the difficulties in predicting SOH by capacity and internal resistance, indirect indexes such as charging time duration [26], IC [33] and differential voltage [34], are referred for SOH prediction. Although these indexes do not directly relate to SOH, they show strong nonlinear correlation with it in the whole lifespan. In other words, if some indirect indexes can be properly extracted from the charge and discharge experiments, a mapping relationship with respect to SOH can thereby be constructed. When data driven learning algorithms are adopted for training, the model prediction precision will depend on the learning ability. Compared with classical NNs, recurrent NNs (RNNs) usually conduct better training jobs due to the capability of describing the implicit characters inside of the signals by inner state variables [35]. Nonetheless, RNNs are limited by finite history information storage, and thus it is difficult, and even impossible, to conduct the long-term prediction with high precision [36]. As a kind of deep learning network, the long short-term memory (LSTM) is a special RNN employed to learn the long-term dependency [37], and has been progressively applied in language modeling [38] and image recognition [39]. Long term historical information can be memorized by special gates in LSTM. Given that battery aging is a long-term process, the LSTM network may be a suitable solution to learn the long-term degradation trend of battery capacity.

Motivated by this, the LSTM is applied in this study to achieve the SOH prediction, and five HFs are extracted from battery charging/discharging data. The grey relational analysis (GRA) and entropy weight method (EWM) are introduced to optimize the HFs. Then, the layer, structure and topology of LSTM are designed to establish the mapping relationship between HFs and SOH. Meanwhile, the Adam algorithm is utilized to optimize the weights and biases of LSTM. Finally, the optimized LSTM is employed to achieve SOH prediction and experimental validations in terms of different types of lithium-ion batteries are conducted to manifest the feasibility of proposed method. The main contributions of this study can be attributed to the following three aspects: (1) Five HFs are extracted from the experimental life cycle data of lithium-ion batteries. (2) The GRA and EWM are employed to enhance the correlation between the extracted HFs and SOH. (3) The LSTM network is applied to achieve the accurate SOH prediction.

The remainder of this paper is arranged as follows. The battery life cycle test is introduced, and the experimental data is analyzed in Section II. Section III illustrates the detailed

extraction procedures of HFs. The mechanism of LSTM and the whole prediction process are elaborated in Section IV. A series of prediction results are analyzed and discussed in Section V, followed by conclusions given in Section VI.

II. BATTERY TEST AND DEGRADATION ANALYSIS

In this study, SOH quantifies degradation degree of lithium-ion batteries and provides reference for replacement or abandonment of batteries. Here, SOH is defined as the ratio of current maximum available capacity Q_{cur} over the nominal value Q_{nom} , as:

$$SOH = \frac{Q_{cur}}{Q_{nom}} \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

A. BATTERY TEST

To investigate degradation of lithium-ion batteries, the repetitive charge and discharge cycle experiment is conducted based on the conventional constant current (CC)-constant voltage (CV) scheme. Five cylindrical lithium-ion batteries belonging to two types are experimented. To simplify the description, five batteries are represented by cell 1 to cell 5 hereinafter. Cells 1 and 2 belong to the 21700 type, and cells 3 to 5 belong to the 18650 type. The positive electrode materials of the five cells are all $\text{LiNi}_{1-x-y}\text{Co}_x\text{Mn}_y\text{O}_2$, and the related parameters are listed in Table I. A complete battery operating cycle consists of three typical stages: charge, discharge as well as rest in between. To ensure safe operation of batteries, related limitations should be carefully set with respect to the specifications. The detailed program of battery life cycle test is detailed as follows.

- 1) In the CC charging mode, cells 1 and 2 are charged with the current of 0.5C (C denotes the battery rated capacity with the unit of Ampere-hour) and cells 3 to 5 are charged with the current of 1C, until their voltages reach the upper limit.
- 2) In the CV charging mode, charge the battery cells with constant voltage, until the current gradually decreases to the cut-off current.
- 3) Remain the cells still for 1 hour.
- 4) In the discharge mode, discharge battery cells 1, 3, 4 and 5 with 2C current and cell 2 with 3C rate, until the voltage reaches the cut-off value.
- 5) Keep the cells still for 1 hour.
- 6) Repeat steps (1) to (5) to finish the cycle test.

TABLE I
RELATED PARAMETERS FOR TWO TYPES BATTERIES

Item	Parameters	
	type 1	type 2
Size	21700	18650
Nominal capacity	4 Ah	2.55 Ah
Charge mode	CC/CV	CC/CV
Charge limited voltage	4.2 V	4.2 V
Charge cut-off current	80 mA	51 mA
Discharge cut-off voltage	2.75 V	2.5 V

B. DEGRADATION DATA ANALYSIS

The degradation curves of battery capacity are shown in Figs. 1 and 2. To attain the extreme performances of batteries, the

hybrid power pulse characterization (HPPC) test is inserted after each 50 cycles' experiment for cells 1 and 2 and after each 30 cycles' experiments for cells 3 to 5. Specially, a urban dynamometer driving schedule (UDDS) test is implemented for cells 2, 3 and 4 after the HPPC test. It can be observed from Fig. 1, the degradation rate of cells 1 and 2 are extraordinarily different, and the degradation rate of cell 2 is much faster than that of cell 1. Comparing with cell 1, higher discharge rated along with UDDS test are additionally imposed on cell 2, and results in faster degradation rate on cell 2. It is worth noting that obvious bulges rise in capacity degradation curves, as shown in Fig. 2, since several testing intervals result in local tiny capacity regeneration, and show certain effect on SOH variation locally.

FIGURE 1. Capacity degradation curves of Cell 1 and Cell 2.

FIGURE 2. Capacity degradation curves of Cells 3-5.

III. EXTRACTION OF HEALTHY FEATURES

As discussed above, data driven methods are required to search features relating with SOH. In real applications, the terminal voltage, current, environment temperature and operating time, can be directly monitored and recorded. In this study, the HFs are extracted from the battery charge and discharge data.

A. FEATURES EXTRACTION

Fig. 3 shows the charging voltage curve of cell 2 with different cycle numbers. As can be found, the duration of CC stage decreases as the cycle experiment goes on, implying intensification of the battery polarization. The capacity mainly depends on the duration of CC charging stage. When

polarization becomes worse, the duration of CC stage will become shorter, leading to the decline of charging capacity. Intuitively, the duration of CC charging stage, denoted by F_1 , can be selected as a HF. In addition, the duration of CV stage becomes longer, and yet the total charge time gradually declines. Nevertheless, by comparing with the variation scope of CC charge duration, the duration of CV mode changed inconspicuously. It is obvious that the proportion of CC charge mode duration occupying the whole charging process can reflect the correlation between the CV duration and SOH, and also amplify the change in the CC duration. Therefore, it is selected as another HF F_2 , as:

$$F_2 = \frac{t_{CC}}{t_{CC} + t_{CV}} \quad (2)$$

where t_{CC} and t_{CV} denote the CC and CV duration in each cycle, respectively.

FIGURE 3. The battery charging process. (a) Charging voltage curves at different cycles. (b) Selection of feature in charging curve.

The variation of discharge voltage curve with different cycle times is shown in Fig. 4. We can find that, as the cycle number increases, the discharge voltage drops faster than before. Since in the cycling experiment, the discharge current is the same in each cycle, the duration of discharging process can directly represent the discharge capacity, and then the SOH can be calculated. In actual operations, we are not likely to measure the residual capacity and monitor the

operating conditions of battery. If the offline tested data can be analyzed to find the hidden relationship between the constant discharge duration and battery SOH, then knowing the constant discharge duration can contribute to SOH estimation. In this context, the discharge duration is adopted as one HF. However, in real-time application, the user seldom allows the full discharge to happen. Thus, to ensure that the discharge duration is effective, we select a section of voltage curve (from 3.6 V to 3.2 V) to replace the discharge the original total discharge duration, as:

$$F_3 = |t_{i1} - t_{i2}| \quad (3)$$

where t_{i1} and t_{i2} denote the instant at the voltages of 3.2 V to 3.6 V, respectively, and F_3 denotes the duration.

FIGURE 4. Feature extraction in the discharging curves.

B. FEATURES EXTRACTION BASED ON IC CURVE

Currently, battery IC variation has been intensively applied in SOH prediction [33]. If the terminal voltage is treated as a function of capacity increment, the relationship between the increased capacity and terminal voltage can be derived to obtain the IC curve. By differentiating the charged capacity over its terminal voltage under the CC charging mode, the slowly varying voltage plateaus can be transformed into an obvious peak on the IC curve. The relationship between the charged capacity and voltage can be described as:

$$\begin{cases} Q = \int Idt \\ V = f(Q), Q = f^{-1}(V) \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

where I is the battery current, Q represents the charge capacity, V denotes the terminal voltage, f represents a mapping function from capacity to voltage, and f^{-1} denotes the reverse function of f . Given that $G = f^{-1}$, the derivative of G can be deduced as:

$$G' = (f^{-1})' = \frac{dQ}{dV} = \frac{Idt}{dV} = I \frac{dt}{dV} \quad (5)$$

When the voltage interval and time interval are short enough, an approximation can be attained, as:

$$\frac{dt}{dV} \approx \frac{\Delta t}{\Delta V} \quad (6)$$

Thus, we can get:

$$\frac{dQ}{dV} = I \frac{\Delta t}{\Delta V} \quad (7)$$

The IC curves are deduced with different voltage intervals. Given a certain voltage interval, the discrete IC can be calculated as:

$$Q_{V_l \rightarrow V_h} = I \Delta t \quad (8)$$

where V_l and V_h denote the lower and higher voltage boundaries of selected section. $Q_{V_l \rightarrow V_h}$ represents the capacity increment in the interval, and Δt denotes the time duration when the voltage increases from V_l to V_h . To calculate the incremental capacity variation, the voltage interval is set to $\Delta V = 1mV$. The IC curve derived from (4) to (8) is shown in Fig. 5. As can be seen, the noise of original IC curve caused by sampling errors hinders further extraction of implicit features. To cope with it, a number of filters have been adopted by researchers to suppress the noise and obtain the smoother IC curve [33]. For ease of simply eliminating the noise, the commonly used first-order low-pass filter is applied, and the filtering result is also shown in Fig. 5. A series of filtered IC curves at different aging status are shown in Fig. 6. Some distinct characteristics can be easily found that, with the increment of cycle number, the peak point gradually moves towards higher voltage, and the peak value of IC decreases and therefore shows the monotonous decline with respect to the capacity degradation. The variation implies that the IC value of peak point and corresponding voltage can effectively characterize the battery degradation, and thus they are also considered as HFs, called F_4 and F_5 hereinafter.

FIGURE 5. The original IC curve and filtered IC curve.

C. GREY RELATIONAL ANALYSIS

To sum up, five HFs, including the CC charge duration F_1 , CC charge ratio F_2 , discharge duration F_3 , IC peak value F_4 and corresponding voltage F_5 , are extracted to predict the battery SOH based on the tested data set. The physical significance of these five HFs are explained as follows: F_1 highlights the polarization phenomenon; F_2 represents the charge ability of battery to some extent; F_3 , reflecting the discharge capacity of battery, is the duration of discharging

the battery from 3.6 V to 3.2 V with the CC mode; F_4 and F_5 denote the peak value of IC curve and the corresponding voltage, which can highlight the subtle changes in the voltage plateau stage. Besides, all the five HF are normalized to eliminate the dimensional impact, and the normalized HF of cell 2 with respect to cycle number are shown in Fig. 7. It can be seen from Fig. 7 that the obvious bulges appeared at the 86th, 101th, 136th and 186th cycle for F_5 , which is caused by the rest operation for a period of time between two adjacent cycles. When the cycle experiment is temporarily stopped and the battery remains still for relatively long time, tiny capacity regeneration will occur. The small change of capacity is enlarged by the IC curve, the peak value decreases and the peak location shifts right slightly. Overall, we can find that each HF varies dramatically with the cycle number. In this study, the correlation between HF and battery SOH is evaluated by GRA [40]. As a crucial method based on the grey system theory, GRA evaluates the correlation among elements according to similarity and dissimilarity of their variation trend. The quantitative analysis based on GRA is to obtain the correlations between reference and comparative sequences, as detailed in [41]. By this manner, the correlations between five HF and SOH are derived and listed in Table II.

FIGURE 6. The features extracted based on IC curves.

FIGURE 7. The evolution trend of HF with cycle numbers.

From Fig. 7 and Table II, we can find that with the increase of cycling number, the extracted HF highlight different variation trend. It can be observed from TABLE II that both F_1 and F_2 show stronger correlation with SOH. In essence, F_1 and F_2 reflect how much electric energy can be charged into the battery, and therefore they should have strong correlation with SOH, which is validated by the calculation results. To sum up, except F_5 of cell 3, all of HF demonstrate strong variation with SOH. Nevertheless, the contribution function of each HF is difficult to evaluate intuitively. To further determine the HF's weight, the EWM is introduced in the following part to improve the correctness.

TABLE II
GREY RELATIONAL GRADES BETWEEN FEATURES AND SOH

Battery Number	Healthy Features				
	F_1	F_2	F_3	F_4	F_5
Cell 1	0.7604	0.7263	0.5540	0.5775	0.5474
Cell 2	0.7768	0.8772	0.6797	0.5389	0.5991
Cell 3	0.7533	0.7338	0.5616	0.5874	0.4809
Cell 4	0.8139	0.7393	0.6667	0.6940	0.5183
Cell 5	0.7111	0.7406	0.6767	0.5690	0.5012

D. ENTROPY WEIGHT METHOD ANALYSIS

Entropy is a measurement for uncertainty in information theory. A common knowledge is that more information can lead to lower uncertainty and consequently lower entropy, which means the system is more orderly, and vice versa [42, 43]. In this study, the entropy weight is employed to evaluate the dispersion of HF, and smaller value indicates higher dispersion of corresponding HF. As a result, the weighting coefficient of HF should be relatively larger, compared with that of other less related HF. The following steps of calculating the entropy weight value are listed as follows:

- 1) Normalize the original HF as in GRA.
- 2) Calculate the proportion of the j th HF in all items for each charge/discharge cycle, as:

$$p_{ij} = \frac{x_{ij}}{\sum_{i=1}^n x_{ij}} \quad (9)$$

where the subscript i denotes the cycle times and subscript j indicates the j th HF.

- 3) Calculate the information entropy weight for each HF:

$$h_j = -\ln^{-1}(n) \times \sum_{i=1}^n (p_{ij} \times \ln p_{ij}) \quad (10)$$

- 4) Calculate the entropy weight value for each HF, as:

$$w_j = \frac{1-h_j}{k - \sum_{j=1}^k h_j}, \quad \sum_{j=1}^k w_j = 1 \quad (11)$$

The value of entropy weight depicts the significance of HF. By calculating (9) to (11), the entropy weights of HF for cell 1 to 5 are shown in Fig. 8. It can be observed that, except F_5 of cells 3, 4 and 5, other entropy weights are smaller and most of them are lower than 0.3. By comparing with the results

derived directly from the GRA, even the grey relational degree and the entropy weight of each HF are different, the extracted HFs strongly correlate with SOH. In other words, a kind of relationship with SOH for each HF really exists. In the next step, the LSTM together with extracted HFs is employed to achieve the SOH prediction.

FIGURE 8. The entropy weight values of HFs.

IV. SOH PREDICTION BASED ON THE LSTM

A. STRUCTURE AND MECHANISM OF LSTM

LSTM is a kind of specialized RNN for solving vanishing gradient problems and gradient explosion problems with long-term dependency [44]. The particular gates in LSTM can make full use of historical information and long-term dependency of time series data. Given the fixed model parameters, the recurrent weight changes with time by conducting the gate control, and the integral scale varies dynamically, thus the vanishing gradient and gradient explosion can be resolved [45]. The network structure of LSTM is described in Fig. 9.

FIGURE 9. The network architecture of LSTM.

As can be seen from Fig. 9, LSTM, similar with classic RNN, is composed of the input layer, hidden layer and output layer. However, the hidden layer in the LSTM network has a specialized memory mechanism, instead of a general neuron. Any read or modification operation can be achieved through controlling of the input gate, forget gate and output gate. Additionally, the information selection of gate is mainly

conducted by the sigmoid function, tanh function or matrix multiplication. The first step of applying LSTM is to decide what information should be discarded by the forget gate, which reads h_{t-1} and x_t , and outputs a value f_t between 0 and 1, as:

$$f_t = \sigma \times (W_f \times [h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_f) \quad (12)$$

where h_{t-1} is the last output of cell state, x_t is the current cell input, σ represents the sigmoid function, W_f is the weight matrix of forget gate, and b_f is the bias of forget gate. Here, the upper bound 1 indicates that the information should be totally kept; and on the contrary, the lower bound 0 means that it should be thoroughly discarded.

The next step is to determine what information should be stored in the memory cell. One part of the input gate i_t , called “sigmoid layer”, decides what information should be updated, and another part, called “tanh layer”, creates the candidate vector a_t based on (13), as:

$$\begin{cases} i_t = \sigma \times (W_i \times [h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_i) \\ a_t = \tanh \times (W_C \times [h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_C) \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

where W_i and W_C denote the weight matrix of sigmoid layer and tanh layer of input gate, respectively; and b_i and b_C represent the bias of sigmoid layer and tanh layer of input gate. Accordingly, the current cell state can be updated by:

$$C_t = f_t \times C_{t-1} + i_t \times a_t \quad (14)$$

Finally, by means of the updated cell state and tanh layer of the output gate, the output of LSTM can be calculated, as:

$$\begin{cases} o_t = \sigma \times (W_o \times [h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_o) \\ h_t = o_t \times \tanh \times C_t \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

where W_o and b_o denote the weight matrix and bias of the output layer, and o_t is the sigmoid layer of output gate.

Based on the introduction of three gates in LSTM network, the whole working process can be summarized as follows. At each step, two types of external signals, current state x_t , last hidden state h_{t-1} and the last cell state C_{t-1} , are received as the inputs of LSTM. For the input signals, each gate determines its output and makes the decision by the logic function. The input signals are mapped by a non-linear transformation into the output of forget gate to generate the new cell state C_t , which is sequentially transformed by a non-linear function and dominated by the dynamic control of output gate. Finally, the LSTM will generate its final output. Next, the training algorithm will be detailed to search the optimal weight matrices and biases for SOH prediction.

B. THE TRAINING OF LSTM NETWORK

In this study, the Adam optimal algorithm is introduced to train the parameters of LSTM, and it is a first-order optimal algorithm with higher computational efficiency, lower RAM occupation, less turning labor and better dominance in solving large-scale parameter optimization, compared with traditional random gradient descent algorithms. Ref. [46] experimentally

highlights that, comparing with the RMSprop [47] and AdaGrad algorithm [48], the Adam algorithm is distinguished in solving local deep learning problems. The Adam algorithm obeys the following update rules. First, at step t , the gradient of optimization objective is calculated, as:

$$g_t = \nabla_{\theta} J(\theta_{t-1}) \quad (16)$$

where $J(\theta)$ represents the objective function with θ , g_t denotes the gradient with θ_{t-1} . At step t , the exponential moving average value of both gradient and squared gradient m_t and v_t , are respectively calculated, as:

$$\begin{cases} m_t = \beta_1 m_{t-1} + (1 - \beta_1) g_t \\ v_t = \beta_2 v_{t-1} + (1 - \beta_2) g_t^2 \end{cases} \quad (17)$$

where β_1 and β_2 are the exponential decay factors accounting for weight distribution and influence incurred by squared gradient. In general, the initial value of m_0 and v_0 is set to zero, m_t and v_t are adjusted to zero in the initial stage of training process. Thus, a modification will be applied to reduce the training error, as:

$$\begin{cases} \hat{m}_t = m_t / (1 - \beta_1) \\ \hat{v}_t = v_t / (1 - \beta_2) \end{cases} \quad (18)$$

where \hat{m}_t and \hat{v}_t are the modified values of m_t and v_t . The parameters is updated as:

$$\theta_t = \theta_{t-1} - \alpha \times \hat{m}_t / (\sqrt{\hat{v}_t} + \varepsilon) \quad (19)$$

where α denotes the learning rate, and ε expresses the smooth coefficient for avoiding the denominator from zero. The remaining parameters in this paper are set to $\beta_1 = 0.9$, $\beta_2 = 0.999$, $\alpha = 0.001$, and $\varepsilon = 10^{-8}$.

C. SOH PREDICTION AND EVALUATION CRITERIONS

Different data sizes are employed to train the network, the remainder of data is harnessed to validate the prediction performance. To evaluate the prediction performance, maximum absolute error (MAE), mean square error (MSE), root-mean-square error (RMSE) and goodness-of-fit R^2 are considered as the criterions. MAE, MSE and RMSE comprehensively evaluate the average prediction performance, of which smaller value implies better prediction precision. Instead, R^2 (varying within [0, 1]) evaluates the correctness of trained model, and higher value (i.e., closer to 1) of R^2 indicates more similar prediction result, compared to the real attribution. The mentioned four criterions are defined as:

$$\begin{cases} MAE = \max |y_i - \hat{y}_i| \\ MSE = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2 \\ RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2} \\ R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^m (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^m (y_i - \bar{y}_i)^2} \end{cases} \quad (20)$$

where n represents the total sample number; y_i and \hat{y}_i are the real value and predicted value of target variable for the i th

sample, respectively; and \bar{y}_i represents the average value. To sum up, the overall SOH prediction flowchart is described in Fig. 10. First, the aforementioned five HF's are extracted from the offline aging data. Then, a certain amount of test data are adopted to train the LSTM, and the optimal model parameters are searched. Finally, the well-tuned model is applied to realize the SOH prediction.

FIGURE 10. The flowchart of proposed SOH estimation algorithm.

In the next section, a series of validations are conducted, and the detailed discussions are performed.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In real applications, the battery aging experiment always costs considerable time for data acquisition. Hence, it should be carefully concerned that at least how much training data is enough for the LSTM to achieve acceptable prediction performance. To evaluate it, the data of cell 1 is utilized to analyze the effect on SOH prediction with respect to different data size, and the data of other cells are adopted to evaluate the model performance on different batteries.

A. SOH PREDICTION WITH SINGLE BATTERY DATA

To analyze the influence on the LSTM caused by the size of training data, 30%, 40%, 50%, 60% and 70% of test data for cell 1 are sequentially employed in model training. As shown in Fig. 11, the general prediction error gradually becomes lower with the increase of data size. When 30% of the total data is employed training, the maximum prediction error is 6.70%, and it is obvious that on the prediction phase, the estimated SOH gradually deviates the real SOH and generates obvious difference in the end of cycle. When 60% and 70% of cycle data are imported to train the model, the maximum prediction error decreases to 1.78% and 1.21%, respectively. In actual applications, the SOH prediction error of less than 3% can be accepted. Hence, we adopt 60% of the cycle data to train the model. The estimation result and error of cell 3 with 60% cycle data for training are illustrated in Fig. 12. It can be seen that most estimation errors are lower than 2%, and yet the maximum error is 4.55%. When the LSTM is employed to predict the next step state of system, the history useful information are remained and the last step information is inputted to the model, which leads to the predicted value

one step behind the real one. Consequently, the estimation error becomes larger in the cycle after a rest on the curve. From Figs. 11 and 12, due to the inconspicuous phenomenon of local capacity regeneration of cell 1, there is no large oscillation in terms of SOH in the whole cycle life, and the estimation error is concentrated; however, the partial estimation error of cell 3 is scattered due to the large oscillation. In total, the proposed model can be predicted SOH with high accuracy for a single battery.

FIGURE 11. The SOH estimation results of cell 1 with different training data. (a) 30% cycle data; (b) 40% cycle data; (c) 50% cycle data; (d) 60% cycle data; (e) 70% cycle data.

B. SOH PREDICTION WITH MULTIPLE BATTERY DATA

To analyze the robustness of proposed algorithm, we employed one battery data as the training data and the other data for test. Figs. 13 to 16 and Table III depict the prediction results and corresponding errors. The prediction result and error of cell 2 with the train model based on cell 1 is shown in Fig. 13, from which we can find that the estimation error is less than 1%. It can therefore be concluded that the SOH decline trend can be well tracked by the proposed model.

To further validate the influence of training data quantity on the estimation error, we employ the data of cell 3 for training, cells 4 and 5 for testing, and also the data of cells 3 and 4 for training and cell 5 for testing. From Figs. 14 and 15, the errors of cells 4 and 5 with cell 3's data as training are 4.70% and 5.99%, respectively. It can be noted that the MSE and RMSE of cell 4 are respectively 18.69×10^{-5} and 1.37%, larger than the others' estimation error. This is arisen by the tiny characteristics difference among cells. The R^2 of cell 4 is 0.9912, close to 1, indicating that the predicted values are similar to real values. From Fig. 14 (a), we can find that the predict trajectory looks the same as the real SOH variation. Through all of the performance criteria, the proposed SOH prediction algorithm shows satisfactory performance. Fig. 16 shows the prediction result and error of cell 5 with the training model from cells 3 and 4. The MAE, MSE and RMSE are 5.39%, 5.20×10^{-5} and 0.72%, respectively, and R^2 is 0.9972.

Compared with the prediction results estimated based on the data of cell 3, the estimation error of cell 5 is smaller and R^2 is closer to 1. Thus, we can conclude that increasing the amount of training data can certainly improve the prediction accuracy of proposed model. It can be noted that we use only 30% of complete cycle life data of cell 1 for training, the maximum estimation error is 6.70%. Although it hardly can obtain large amounts of offline battery data for training in real application, the proposed model can still well track the SOH trend with the acceptable error. To sum up, the prediction results manifest that the proposed algorithm and corresponding trained model can predict the battery SOH with preferable accuracy.

FIGURE 12. The SOH estimation results and error of cell 3.

FIGURE 13. The SOH estimation results and error of cell 2 with data of cell 1 for training.

FIGURE 14. The SOH estimation results of cell 4 with cell 3's data for training.

FIGURE 15. The SOH estimation results and error of cell 5 with data of cell 3 for training.

TABLE III
SOH ESTIMATION ERRORS

Training	Testing	Error Criterion			
		MAE (%)	MSE (10^{-5})	RMSE (%)	R^2
Cell 1	Cell 2	0.73	0.415	0.20	0.9982
Cell 3	Cell 4	4.70	18.69	1.37	0.9912
Cell 3	Cell 5	5.99	9.05	0.95	0.9951
Cell 3, 4	Cell 5	5.39	5.20	0.72	0.9972

FIGURE 16. The SOH estimation results and error of cell 5 with data of cells 3 and 4 for training.

C. COMPARISON OF PREDICTION RESULTS WITH DIFFERENT METHODS

To further evaluate the performance of LSTM, the single Elman NN, SVM and GPR algorithms are respectively applied

for the SOH estimation of cells 1 and 3. For the sake of fair comparison, 60% of the battery cycle data is utilized to train the model, and the remaining 40% data is employed to validate the precision. The predicted results and errors are shown in Figs. 17 to 18 and Tables IV to V. It can be seen from Fig. 18 and Table V that for cell 3, with relatively less cycling data, the LSTM and other three methods can track the variation trajectory of SOH precisely and achieve the preferable prediction accuracy; whereas for cell 1, the data length is much more than that of cell 3, and the LSTM can attain the smaller prediction error, of which the MAE, MSE, RMSE and R^2 for cell 1 are 1.32%, 2.34×10^{-5} , 0.48% and 0.9944, respectively. Although the prediction results of SVM and Elman NN can roughly reflect the variation trend of SOH, their prediction errors are much larger than that of the LSTM. The prediction result of GPR method shown in Fig. 17 clearly deviates from the true SOH value, manifesting that the GPR method is not suitable for time series prediction with large sample data and long-term dependence. Additionally, it is worth noting that the Gaussian function is selected as the kernel function of SVM to attain better prediction accuracy, and it leads to intensive calculation during the hyper-parameter optimization and costs much more time than the LSTM. To sum up, the LSTM not only exhibits higher prediction accuracy and faster operation, but also shows more reliability in predicting the capacity degradation process with long-term dependence, compared with the Elman NN, SVM and GPR methods.

FIGURE 17. The estimation results for cell 1 with different methods.

FIGURE 18. The estimation results for cell 3 with different methods.

TABLE IV

SOH ESTIMATION ERRORS FOR CELL 1 WITH DIFFERENT METHODS

Methods	Error Criterion			
	MAE (%)	MSE (10 ⁻⁵)	RMSE (%)	R ²
LSTM	1.32	2.34	0.48	0.9944
Elman NN	3.35	22.29	1.49	0.9467
SVM	1.98	10.84	1.04	0.9741
GPR	5.98	130	3.55	0.6979

TABLE V
SOH ESTIMATION ERRORS FOR CELL 3 WITH DIFFERENT METHODS

Methods	Error Criterion			
	MAE (%)	MSE (10 ⁻⁴)	RMSE (%)	R ²
LSTM	4.67	1.66	1.29	0.9935
Elman NN	4.93	3.49	1.87	0.9864
SVM	2.41	0.97	0.99	0.9962
GPR	3.11	2.93	1.71	0.9885

VI. CONCLUSION

In this paper, a SOH estimation method based on the LSTM is proposed for lithium-ion batteries. Firstly, the battery charge and discharge voltage curve and IC curve are analyzed for extracting the HFs, then the GRA and EWM are adopted to refine the extracted HFs. Based on the selected five HFs, the LSTM is employed to achieve the SOH prediction, and meanwhile, the Adam algorithm is leveraged to find the optimal model parameters. For the single battery, it is validated that with the 60% cycle data for model training, the estimation error of SOH can reach a maximum value of 4.55%. Also, when only one battery data is used for training, the SOH estimation error of other cells remains less than 5.99%. Moreover, the experimental results illustrate that, by comparing with the Elman NN, SVM and GPR methods, the proposed method can predict the SOH with preferable accuracy and certain robustness. It can also be indicated that the proposed method shows certain potential for real applications.

The SOH estimation is finished based on the single battery cell in this research. For further development and universality, SOH estimation of battery packs should be investigated in our next research plan, and moreover the precision of SOH should be improved with incorporation of other advanced algorithms. In addition, the SOH estimation only based on partial charging and discharging conditions would be also our research direction. Furthermore, how to extract relative health features based on time-varying current and partial charge and discharge cycle data to conduct SOH prediction will also be our research focus.

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